

Multidimensional Model of Business Performance with Financial Literacy Integration Mediated by Loan Repayment Commitment and Moderated by MSE Business Innovation on the Island of Madura

Fadali Rahman¹, Heri Pratikto², F. Danardana Murwani³, Puji Handayati⁴

¹²³⁴Faculty of Economics and Business, State University of Malang
¹University of Madura

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between financial literacy and business performance, emphasising loan repayment commitment as a mediator and business innovation as a moderator. Focusing on micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in Madura Island's food and beverage sector, the study explores how financial literacy influences loan repayment commitment and business success. Hierarchical regression analysis and structural equation modelling (SEM) using AMOS version 24 were employed on the data collected from 373 MSEs. The findings revealed that financial literacy significantly enhances MSE performance. Although financial literacy has a limited direct impact on loan repayment commitment, it also strengthens its effect on business performance. In addition, loan repayment commitment mediates the link between financial literacy and business outcomes. These results highlight the critical role of financial literacy and innovation in improving MSE performance and offer actionable insights for policymakers and entrepreneurs.

Keywords: financial literacy, loan repair commitment, business innovation, business performance.

A. INTRODUCTION

The Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) sector makes a major contribution to Indonesia's economic growth. MSEs are critical to any country's economic development and play a significant role worldwide (Gashi, 2016). The MSE sector is particularly prominent in Indonesia, accounting for 99% of all business entities. Their contribution to the country's GDP is substantial, reaching 60.5%, and they also provide employment for 96.9% of the total national workforce. MSEs are adaptable because they can operate in any area and carry out a range of commercial operations in both urban and rural environments (Khalique & Abdul, 2018; Meldona et al., 2023).

Many people believe that MSEs are essential for efforts to reduce poverty because of their capacity to produce jobs (Adomako et al., 2015; Rahadjeng et al., 2023). By generating tax income, micro and small enterprises (MSEs) not only support regional development but also employment and economic progress. Furthermore, they demonstrated resilience during periods of monetary crisis, maintaining stability in challenging economic conditions (Akbar, 2021). Empowering MSEs offers significant potential for stimulating local economies, and serves as a vital source of income for improving household welfare. In other countries, such as Nigeria, MSEs have made significant contributions to economic advancement, providing a foundation for entrepreneurs and offering solutions to unemployment challenges while also promoting marketing growth (Eniola & Entebang, 2015).

Micro and Small Businesses (MSEs) were resilient in the face of the economic crisis that started in 1997, and they have been crucial in the country's economic recovery by making major contributions to employment and gross domestic product (GDP) (Aisyah, Pratikto, Wardoyo, & Restuningdiah, 2024; Husaeni, U.A, 2019). The success can be attributed to their

lack of reliance on foreign debt and minimal dependence on bank loans. Additionally, many MSE sectors such as agriculture, trade, and home-based industries are not reliant on foreign raw materials. This self-sufficiency has enabled MSEs to withstand economic pressures, including policy shifts such as fuel price increases, which typically increase raw material costs for businesses. This resilience underscores their capacity to endure challenging situations.

Indonesia's economic growth in 2020 experienced a notable decline, according to data from the Central Statistics Agency (CSA), from 2.97% in the first quarter to -5.32% in the second. This marked a critical turning point as economic activity began shifting from traditional methods to digital platforms. Digital transformation, fuelled by advancements in information technology, artificial intelligence, automation, and increasing accessibility of digital platforms, has been instrumental in supporting various sectors. In addition to having a positive effect on the general population, it has helped businesses and MSEs through financial technology and e-commerce, students through e-learning, and the government through e-government programmes (Maghfiroh & Biduri, 2022). In response to these changes, all segments of society were compelled to adapt to fulfilling basic needs. Consequently, the economy began to recover in the third quarter, with the growth rate improving, although it remained fragile, reaching -2.07% in the fourth quarter (www.bps.go.id; Ratnawati, et al., 2022).

MSEs flourished during the pandemic by embracing innovation, and many of them made use of a variety of financing options provided by financial institutions. These schemes were designed to create a mutually beneficial relationship, ensuring that both parties could thrive while fostering confidence in timely loan repayment. Support from financial institutions was critical in helping MSEs navigate challenging times and in developing new strategies for survival and growth. On Madura Island, the expansion of MSEs reflects this trend, demonstrating how innovation and financial support contributed to resilience and continued development during the crisis.

Figure 1.1 Number of MSEs on the island of Madura from 2015-2021

The data indicate that, for the previous seven years, MSE growth has increased steadily. Notably, the number of new MSEs established in 2016 increased significantly to 2,993, surpassing the growth observed in the subsequent years. In 2017, there was a more

moderate rise in 386 MSEs, followed by an uptick in 2018, with the creation of 933 new enterprises. However, in 2019, the growth slowed to just 312 MSEs, marking a smaller increase compared with previous and later years. The subsequent years saw a steady rebound, with 1,289 new MSEs in 2020 and further growth in 2021, reaching 1,722 MSEs (Rahman & Pratikno, 2022). This consistent expansion of MSEs has contributed significantly to reducing poverty levels by increasing employment opportunities (Adomako et al., 2015), while their continuous growth remains crucial for sustaining national economic development (Agustina, Winarno, Pratikto, Narmaditya, & Filianti, 2020; Morina D. Gashi, 2016).

The annual increase in the number of MSEs demonstrates their resilience in withstanding both international and national economic crises (Kachkach & Uchida, 2022; Rochayatun, Pratikto, Wardoyo, & Handayati, 2023). This study investigates the business performance on Madura Island by analysing several key variables, including financial literacy, loan repayment commitment as a mediating factor, and business innovation as a moderating influence. Financial literacy is a crucial life skill for consumers, yet many individuals worldwide still lack access to this essential knowledge, which restricts their financial behaviour (Sharif et al., 2020). Higher financial literacy is associated with reduced debt anxiety (Noviarini, Coleman, Roberts, & Whiting, 2021), as it enhances understanding of the borrowing process from financial institutions. The relationship between financial literacy, risk tolerance, and debt anxiety is complex and varies among groups. For instance, in Latin America, the personal loan market has grown approximately 20% annually over the past decade (Farías, 2018), with loans provided by financial institutions to support consumption needs, including essential and educational expenses, as well as business sustainability (Aisyah et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the exploration of financing sources for MSEs highlights several challenges and causal factors, with the goal of leveraging innovative methods to enhance financing opportunities, such as crowdsourcing. Establishing a supportive regulatory framework is essential for promoting the long-term growth and development (Eniola & Entebang, 2015). Research reveals that the association between financial access and the expansion of MSEs in developing nations is favourably and considerably moderated by financial literacy (Okello et al. 2017). Access to financial resources and financial literacy have a substantial and favourable impact on the expansion of MSEs in these areas. To support this, MSE communities benefit from financial education through regular study activities organised by alumni and promotional efforts aimed at improving financial management skills within cooperatives. Additionally, financial understanding is extended to the guardians of Islamic boarding school students, who in turn share this knowledge with the wider community. This approach helps in disseminating financial management information and aims to address issues related to mobile banking by providing a more straightforward alternative (Rahman, Pratikto, Murwani, & Handayati, 2024).

Providing loans is a core function in the financial sector to generate profits; however, it carries significant risk, necessitating stringent risk management and oversight (Putra & Suardhika, 2018). Social capital among entrepreneurs plays a crucial role in enhancing small business productivity through various channels of corporate financing mediation (Boudreaux, Clarke, & Jha, 2022). This social capital includes different forms such as supplier credit, customer credit, and loans from friends and family. The size of a loan is a key indicator of the financial support extended by institutions to their members, with the loan amount directly affecting business development (Sriyono, 2021). The significance of the loan amount lies in its potential to improve business operations, thereby facilitating smoother repayment and benefiting members' overall financial stability (Kachkach & Uchida, 2022; Realita, Pratikto, Wardoyo, & Hermawan, 2023).

Research conducted by Rifantama and Suryaningrum (2022) demonstrate that financing from financial institutions, when used as a mediating variable, significantly influences both entrepreneurial competence and MSE performance. The ratio of long-term loans decreases in correlation with the strength of the relationship between financial institutions and MSEs, measured by the duration or period of financing (Kachkach & Uchida, 2022). These findings align with predictions and suggest that MSEs consider the advantages of the information provided by financial institutions and the associated liquidation costs when deciding on the maturity of their loans.

The trend toward business models has gained significant traction among practitioners, driven by several interacting factors, such as the widespread adoption of digital technologies, particularly the Internet, the deregulation of various industries, and the harmonisation of market regulations (Haftor & Costa, 2022). Innovation, defined as an idea, product, event, or method perceived as new by an individual or group, whether through invention or discovery (Muchtar, 2016) is crucial for achieving specific goals and addressing particular challenges. An essential trait of successful entrepreneurs is their innovation capacity. According to Jabani and Aris (2018), innovation is vital and plays a key role in marketing, as it enables market participants to develop unique advantages that distinguish them from competitors (Rahadjeng, Pratikto, Mukhlis, Restuningdiah, & Mala, 2023; Rahman, F, Sudarmiatin, Hermawan, 2023).

Innovation is often seen as a component of organizational culture that reflects how open an organisation is to new ideas (Rajapathirana and Hui 2018). On the other hand, an organisation's capacity for innovation refers to its capacity to accept and use novel concepts, procedures, and goods (Hartini, 2012). The extent of innovation is typically assessed on a continuum, where a lower level indicates a weaker adoption of innovation by individuals or units within the organisation (Soetjipto et al., 2023). By contrast, a higher level of innovation demonstrates the robust adoption of new practices. Manalu (2022) asserts that creative people are necessary for MSEs to innovate and perform successfully, especially in the food industry. (Soetjipto et al., 2023). Implementing innovative marketing practices such as new or modified product designs, retail strategies, and promotional or pricing schemes is crucial for achieving superior performance (Agustina et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2022).

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) places strong emphasis on evaluating an organisation's internal assets and competencies, emphasising their critical function in developing competitive advantage strategies. Resources are viewed as inputs that empower a company to perform its activities and achieve objectives. By leveraging these internal assets effectively, organisations can differentiate themselves and maintain a competitive edge in the market. Although word resources are often used in context, the meaning of resources in the RBV is often confused. Therefore, it is necessary to distinguish between strategic and nonstrategic resources. Money and tangible assets such as houses and cars can be considered valuable resources in everyday life. However, in an organizational context, such resources are not considered strategic, because competitors can easily obtain them. Consequently, companies cannot rely solely on shared resources to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage. Wernerfelt first proposed the Resource-Based View (RBV) hypothesis in his groundbreaking paper "Resource-Based View of the Firm" (Wernerfelt, 1984), which established the foundation for RBV theory. However, earlier researchers, such as Kenneth Andrews in 1971 and Edith Penrose in 1959, also foresaw the fundamental ideas of RBV.

2. Knowledge-Based View (KBV) theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) gives way to the Knowledge-Based View (KBV), which offers a thorough theoretical foundation for understanding intellectual capital. This asserts that knowledge in its diverse forms is a valuable resource (Rangone, 1999). Its role is to enhance human capital involvement, enabling companies to address challenges more effectively and efficiently (Chen 2010). This emphasis on human resource development has led to more structured and dominant approaches to managing human capital. Human resources are seen as integral parts of companies, and they are essential for the management, planning, organising, coordinating, and assessing of other resources (Mahoney, 2018). From a knowledge-based perspective, firms establish a competitive advantage by creating new knowledge through the integration of existing information. This concept aligns with RBV theory, which asserts that companies must have unique attributes that make it challenging for competitors to replicate or imitate their advantages. With this uniqueness, the company can obtain a profit based on the creations that have been implemented because this uniqueness can attract consumer interest in purchasing products issued by the company.

3. Green Finance Theory

Green financing refers to a financial scheme that provides loans to businesses committed to environment-friendly practices. When conducting credit analysis, banks or other financial institutions must consider the environmental impact of the business and assess how it mitigates potential environmental harm (Yuliawati, Rani, & Assyofa, 2017). According to government regulations, borrowers or business entities seeking green

financing must demonstrate efforts to minimise energy consumption and adhere to 3R principles: reduce, reuse, and recycle in their business operations (Rahman & Handayati, 2023).

4. Micro and Small Enterprises (UMK)

Micro businesses are defined as profitable ventures owned by people or individual business entities that satisfy certain requirements set forth by the law in Article 1, Chapter 1 of Law No. 20 of 2008. Government Regulation No. 7 of 2021, which addresses the protection, empowerment, and facilitation of cooperatives and micro, small, and medium-sized businesses, reaffirms that micro businesses are profitable ventures owned by private individuals or businesses that satisfy the requirements of the regulations.

Regulations in each country and locality may have different requirements for micro and small enterprises, but generally speaking, these are determined by factors such as staff size, yearly revenue, and total assets (Rahman, Sudarmiati, & Hermawan, 2023). According to Law No. 20 of 2008, an annual business turnover of up to IDR 300,000,000 (three hundred million rupiah) and commercial assets worth no more than IDR 50,000,000 (50 million rupiah), excluding land and buildings utilised for company purposes, are considered micro companies. Government Regulation No. 7 of 2021, on the other hand, mandates that micro businesses have annual sales revenues not to exceed IDR 2,000,000,000 (two billion rupiah) and business assets valued at up to IDR 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiah), excluding land and buildings. This regulation focuses on the facilitation, protection, and empowerment of cooperatives and micro-, small-, and medium-sized enterprises.

C. RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, researchers conducted research using quantitative methods. The design of this study is as follows:

Figure 3.1. Conceptual Framework
Source: (Shankar & Jain, 2021)

Information:

- a. Financial Literasi (FL)
- b. Loan Repayment Commitment (LRC)
- c. Innovation Business (IB)
- d. Business Performance (BP)

Research Hypothesis:

- 1) The performance of micro and small enterprises' (MSEs') is positively and significantly impacted by financial literacy, which improves their capacity to handle money wisely and improves overall business outcomes.
- 2) Financial literacy significantly and positively influences the commitment to repay loans, thus enhancing borrowers' adherence to repayment schedules.
- 3) The repayment of loans has a favourable and substantial impact on the performance of micro and small businesses (MSEs), which helps ensure operational success.
- 4) Business innovation increases the influence of loan repayment obligations as a mediating element, thus strengthening the correlation between financial literacy and MSE performance.
- 5) Better business results are obtained when business innovation amplifies the impact of financial literacy on MSE performance.
- 6) The favourable effect of financial knowledge on business success is enhanced by the mediating role of loan repayment commitment in the relationship between financial literacy and MSE business performance.

This research uses purposive sampling, a non-probability technique in which the researcher selects samples according to specific criteria. The criteria for selecting the respondents were as follows:

- a. Micro and small enterprises (MSEs) are located on Madura Island.
- b. On Madura Island, MSEs are registered with the Micro and Small Business Cooperative Service.
- c. MSEs maintain simple financial records and reports.
- d. The MSEs obtained loans from Sharia cooperatives..
- e. MSEs are adept at utilising financial transaction and payment systems that accept both cash and non-cash.

Non-Probability Sampling with a defined quota was used in this study to select respondents up to a predefined number of samples using criteria that support the research goals. Every person in the population does not have an equal chance of being included in the sample when using this technique. The Slovin technique was used to calculate the sample size for this investigation using a 95% confidence level and 5% sampling error.

The researchers used the Raosoft sample size calculator, an online application made specifically for this purpose, to determine the sample size. Raosoft's computations indicated that 373 business units would be the necessary sample size for this study.

D. RESEARCH RESULTS

The study's respondent distribution revealed that 40.2% of participants were men and 59.8% were women, suggesting that a greater proportion of women than men work on MSEs. The respondents' ages were distributed as follows: 97 were between the ages of 17 and 30 (26%); 156 were between the ages of 31 and 45 (41.8%); 109 were between the ages of 46 and 60 (29.5%); and 11 were over the age of 60 (3%). According to the data, the age group of 31–45 years accounts for the largest share of MSE responders, followed by 46–60 years.

Among the respondents, 121 owned businesses exclusively in the food sector, accounting for 32.6%, while 58 owned businesses solely in the beverage sector, accounting for 15.6%. In addition, 194 respondents (51.8 %) operated businesses in both the food and beverage sectors. Regarding the length of time businesses had been operating, 51 respondents had businesses running for 1-5 to years (13.7%), 250 respondents had businesses running for 6-10 years (67.1%), 23 respondents had businesses running for 11-15 years (6.1%), 18 respondents had businesses running for 16-20 years (4.9%), 12 respondents had businesses running for 21-25 years (3.1%), and 19 respondents had businesses running for over 25 years (5.1%). This suggests that most of the firms owned by the respondents had been in operation for six to ten years.

Table 1.1 Results of Regression Weights SEM Analysis

Variable Relationships	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Label
LRC <--- FL	-,318	,174	-1,827	,068	par_17
BP <--- FL	,333	,060	5,514	***	par_14
BP <--- LRC	-,025	,049	-,503	,615	par_15
SM <--- FL	1,000				
PI <--- FL	1,080	,067	16,184	***	par_3
SK <--- FL	,973	,060	16,299	***	par_4
KK <--- FL	,821	,050	16,552	***	par_5
PK <--- FL	,944	,063	14,887	***	par_6
PY <--- BP	1,000				
SMS <--- BP	1,002	,092	10,883	***	par_7
JP <--- BP	1,141	,103	11,036	***	par_8
PS <--- BP	1,096	,101	10,903	***	par_9
US <--- BP	1,073	,101	10,568	***	par_10
KPY <--- LRC	1,000				
KP <--- LRC	1,023	,032	31,566	***	par_11
PTW <--- LRC	1,289	,065	19,790	***	par_12

Source: Data processed 2023

Every indicator or dimension for the latent variables, as indicated by the data displayed in the table, satisfies the significance requirements, with probability (P) values less than 0.05 and critical ratio (CR) values greater than 1.96. However, the effect of loan repayment commitment on business performance (CR value of -0.503 and P value of 0.615) and the impact of financial literacy on loan repayment commitment (CR value of -1.827 and P value of 0.068) are the two indicators that do not show statistical significance.

Univariate outlier evaluation identifies observations with extreme values that deviate significantly from others owing to their unique characteristics. This involves analysing the Z score values of the research data, with any observation having a Z score greater than ± 3.0 , classified as an outlier. Univariate analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.

Table 2. Outlier Data Results

Zscore	N	Min	Max	C.S	Items	Respondents
Zscore FL	373	30,016	59,249	29,59	10	19
Zscore LRC	373	24,63	82,753	24,32	7	18
Zscore IB	373	26,532	54,906	26,12	8	18
Zscore BP	373	20,816	36,655	20,52	5	11
Jumlah		101,994	233,563	100,55	39	81
Mean		25,50	58,39	25,14		

Source: Data processed 2023

The data processing results for testing outliers show that each variable contained univariate outliers, as indicated in the table. These outlier data points will not be removed from the analysis, as they accurately reflect the actual situation, and there is no specific reason related to the respondent's profile that would justify their exclusion from the analysis (Ferdinand, 2005).

Table 3. Standardized Residual Covarian

	FL	LR C	BP	PT W	KP Y	US	PS	JP	S M S	PY	PK	K K	SK	PI	S M	PN N	PT D	PB D
FL	1,00																	
LRC	,541	1,00																
BP	,765	,451	1,00															
PTW	,412	,761	,343	1,00														
KP	,511	,943	,426	,718	1,00													
KPY	,507	,937	,423	,713	,883	1,00												
US	,556	,328	,727	,250	,309	,307	1,00											
PS	,585	,345	,765	,263	,326	,327	,557	1,00										
JP	,598	,352	,781	,268	,332	,330	,568	,598	1,00									
SMS	,584	,344	,763	,262	,325	,322	,555	,584	,596	1,00								
PY	,446	,263	,583	,200	,248	,246	,424	,446	,455	,444	1,00							
PK	,713	,386	,546	,294	,364	,362	,397	,418	,426	,416	,318	1,00						
KK	,774	,419	,592	,319	,395	,392	,430	,453	,462	,452	,345	,552	1,00					
SK	,765	,414	,585	,315	,398	,386	,428	,448	,457	,446	,341	,546	,592	1,00				

PI	.76	.41	.58	.31	.38	.38	.42	.44	.45	.44	.33	.54	.58	.58	1.0				
	1	2	2	3	8	6	3	5	5	4	9	3	9	2	00				
SM	.82	.44	.62	.33	.42	.41	.45	.48	.49	.48	.36	.58	.63	.62	.62	1.0			
	2	5	9	9	0	7	8	1	2	0	7	7	6	9	6	00			
PNN	.43	.48	.36	.37	.45	.45	.26	.27	.28	.27	.21	.30	.33	.33	.35	1.0			
	3	6	4	0	9	6	4	8	4	7	2	9	5	1	0	6	00		
PTD	.57	.64	.47	.48	.60	.59	.34	.36	.37	.36	.27	.40	.44	.43	.43	.46	.43	1.0	
	0	0	8	7	3	9	8	6	4	5	9	7	1	6	4	9	6	00	
PBD	.40	.45	.34	.34	.43	.42	.24	.26	.26	.26	.19	.29	.31	.31	.31	.33	.31	.41	1.0
	7	7	1	8	1	8	8	1	7	1	9	0	5	1	0	5	2	0	00

Source: Data processed 2023

The results show that no standardised residual covariance values exceed ± 2.58 (Ferdinand, 2005). This suggests that the data did not require further modelling adjustments in relation to the model developed in this study.

Table 4. Results of Hierarchical Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.762 ^b	.580	.576	2.103	.094	82.308	1	368	.000
2	.774 ^c	.599	.591	2.064	.019	5.667	3	365	.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), LRC, FL, IB

b. Predictors: (Constant), LRC, FL, IB, int2, int1

Source: Data processed 2023

The table shows that Model 1's R-squared value, which examines the connection between loan repayment commitment, financial literacy, and business performance, is 0.580. In Model 2, which includes the moderator variable of business innovation, the R-squared value increases to 0.599. Additionally, the R-square value in Model 2, which incorporates the interaction variables (X1*Z) and (X2*Z), shows a change in R-square of 0.019 from Model 1. This indicates a significant improvement in the predictive power with the inclusion of moderator and interaction variables. The statistically significant findings imply that in terms of how it affects company performance, business innovation successfully modifies the relationship between financial literacy and loan payback commitment.

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the influence of financial literacy on business performance has a CR value of 5.514 and P value of 0.000. With a CR value exceeding 1.96 and a P value below 0.05, this suggests that financial literacy has a substantial impact on business performance. Thus, there is evidence for the second hypothesis (H1). Nonetheless, the effect of financial literacy on commitment to repay loans has a CR value of -1.827 and a P value of 0.068. The required CR value of 1.96 and a P value of less than 0.05 are not met by this. Consequently, the fourth hypothesis (H2) was unfounded. Similarly, -0.503 is the CR value for the impact of loan payback promises on firm performance.

The data processing results showed that with Sig. F Change of 0.000, the R-squared value for the contribution of company innovation to enhancing the impact of financial literacy on business success, as mediated by loan repayment promises, is 0.599. This suggests that financial literacy, as mediated by loan payback obligations, has a positive impact on business

performance through business innovation, validating the seventh hypothesis (H4) of this study. Furthermore, using Sig. F Change of 0.001, the R-squared value for the contribution of business innovation to enhancing the impact of financial literacy on business success is 0.580. This implies that the impact of financial literacy on business success is amplified by business innovation, hence bolstering the eighth hypothesis (H5). Additionally, the mediating effect of loan repayment commitment has a t count of 12.317 compared to a t-table value of 1.966, despite the fact that the CR values for the effects of financial literacy on loan repayment commitment and business performance are -1.827 and -0.503, respectively, with P value of 0.068 and 0.615, respectively. This finding suggests that the impact of financial literacy on business performance is largely mediated by loan payback commitment, which validates the tenth hypothesis (H6).

E. DISCUSSION

The results of this study demonstrate that financial literacy significantly enhances the performance of micro and small enterprises (MSEs). Higher levels of financial literacy equip business owners with the ability to manage capital effectively, prepare accurate financial reports, and design sound business plans, ultimately improving their business outcomes. Policymakers and financial institutions can leverage this finding by developing targeted training programs that enhance the financial literacy of MSE owners. Such initiatives could focus on budgeting, cash flow management, and investment strategies to ensure that entrepreneurs are better prepared to sustain and grow their businesses.

However, the lack of a statistically significant relationship between financial literacy and loan repayment commitment highlights the complexity of loan repayment behaviour. This finding suggests that while MSE owners may possess adequate financial knowledge, external factors, such as cash flow volatility or unexpected market challenges, may hinder timely loan repayments. Financial institutions could address this gap by providing more flexible repayment structures or offering support programs tailored to the unique circumstances. Moreover, embedding financial counselling or mentorship into loan packages may encourage disciplined repayment behaviour.

Similarly, the absence of a significant link between loan repayment commitment and business performance indicates that loan compliance alone may not drive success directly. This finding underscores the need for a broader approach to financial management beyond the repayment discipline. Policymakers should emphasise comprehensive business development programs that integrate financial literacy, innovation training, and market expansion strategies to maximise their impact on MSE performance.

This study also emphasises the pivotal role of business innovation in strengthening the relationship between financial literacy and MSE performance. Innovation enables businesses to capitalise on their financial knowledge and improve resource allocation, risk management, and market adaptability. For instance, MSEs that innovate in areas, such as product development, process efficiency, and marketing strategies, are better positioned to

achieve sustainable growth. Policymakers and industry stakeholders should foster an innovation-friendly ecosystem by providing grants, tax incentives, and access to technology for the MSEs.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that business innovation enhances the direct effects of financial literacy and strengthens the mediating role of loan repayment commitment. This finding highlights the potential of integrating innovation with financial literacy programs to maximise business outcomes. Entrepreneurs trained to innovate while maintaining financial discipline can access funding more confidently, improving their overall performance. Financial institutions can explore the development of innovation-linked financing models that reward innovative MSEs with lower interest rates or extended credit lines.

This study's theoretical contributions, grounded in the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Knowledge-Based View (KBV), further validate the importance of financial literacy as a critical resource for MSEs. These frameworks suggest that financial knowledge, when combined with innovative capabilities, creates a unique and nonreplicable competitive advantage for businesses. However, the findings also suggest that the correlation between financial literacy and loan repayment obligations is not straightforward. Financial knowledge alone may not guarantee disciplined repayment behaviour, necessitating further exploration of the behavioural and contextual factors that influence loan commitments.

To maximise the practical impact of this research, future studies should provide actionable recommendations for financial institutions, policymakers, and MSE owners. For example, policymakers can prioritise financial literacy and innovation as the core components of national MSE development strategies. Simultaneously, financial institutions can design products that incentivise both innovation and disciplined financial behaviour. By addressing these interconnected factors, stakeholders can create a supportive environment that fosters sustainable growth in MSEs.

In conclusion, this study underscores the critical interplay among financial literacy, business innovation, and MSE performance. While financial literacy lays the foundation for better decision making, innovation amplifies its impact by unlocking growth opportunities. The findings call for collaborative efforts between policymakers, financial institutions, and entrepreneurs to create targeted interventions that enhance financial literacy, encourage innovation, and address barriers to disciplined loan repayments. These efforts will ultimately contribute to the long-term success and sustainability.

F. CONCLUSION

This hypothesis is supported by the fact that financial literacy significantly and favourably affects the business performance on Madura Island. The research results can be interpreted to indicate that the pattern seen shows a positive correlation between the level of literacy or financial knowledge of MSEs and the performance of the business they run. An adequate level of financial understanding allows MSEs to manage capital more effectively, prepare accurate financial reports, and design targeted business plans. Financial literacy has no

discernible beneficial effects on commitment to repay loans. The study's findings indicate that MSEs' commitment to loan repayment was not significantly impacted by its degree of financial literacy. This means that MSEs with high financial literacy do not necessarily have a strong commitment to repaying loans. Conversely, someone with low financial literacy may have high commitment to repaying loans.

Loan repayment obligations have no appreciable positive impact on MSE business performance. Stated differently, the study framework failed to demonstrate a significant and quantifiable correlation between the degree of MSEs' loan repayment commitment and its company's performance. This research shows that, in this particular context, there is no substantial association between MSEs' loan repayment commitment and its business performance, despite the fact that loan repayment commitment is a key feature of financial management. Nonetheless, business innovation amplifies the impact of spirituality on MSE business performance. This suggests that, while direct loan repayment commitment may not significantly impact performance, the integration of innovative practices can amplify the positive effects of high spirituality on business outcomes.

Business innovation enhances the influence of financial literacy on MSE business performance, with loan repayment obligations serving as a mediating factor. The results demonstrate that the level of business innovation undertaken by business owners strengthens the positive influence of their financial literacy and spirituality on increasing their commitment to repaying loans. Furthermore, this increasing loan repayment commitment, in turn, provides a significantly positive contribution to the achievement of actual MSE business performance. Thus, loan repayment commitment serves as a mediator between business innovation and the indirect effect of financial literacy on MSE business performance, both enhancing and moderating. Financial literacy has a strong effect on business performance in terms of business innovation. The owner's financial literacy has a beneficial impact on boosting the MSE's actual performance to a greater extent, as the level of business innovation introduced increases. Stated differently, when financial literacy is combined with innovations in products, processes, and marketing tactics, its beneficial effects on MSEs' sales performance, earnings, and asset growth are amplified.

The association between financial literacy and MSE business performance is influenced by the degree of commitment to loan payback, which acts as a mediator. This indicates that the commitment of business actors to repay loans serves as a mediating factor in this environment, indicating how their financial literacy affects the MSEs they manage. The relationship between financial literacy and MSE business performance is mediated by loan repayment commitment. The study's findings show that the degree of loan payback commitment acts as a mediator, affecting the connection between financial literacy and MSE performance. In other words, the findings of this research show that business actors' commitment to repay loans functions as a connecting or intermediary factor that conveys the impact of the level of financial understanding on how well the MSE business performs.

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